

1 **Epigenetic reprogramming by DNMT1 following fertilization of the oocyte in zygotic activation**
2 **through DMRT2 and TET2.**

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7 We discovered a pathway through which epigenetic reprogramming of the zygote occurs following
8 fertilization of the oocyte between the first and second cell divisions of the embryo using a DNA
9 demethylation process and proceeding through the function of the maintenance DNA methyltransferase
10 *DNMT1*. The mechanism involved activation of doublesex and mab-3 related transcription factor 2 *DMRT2*
11 and featured the function of the ten-eleven translocation (TET1) enzyme *TET2*.

12 Citations

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